

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF DEMOGRAPHY IN UZBEKISTAN, POPULATION COMPOSITION

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Annotation: *In this article, we will study the demographics, register the population, determine the composition of the population on the basis of demographic data, study the known facts about the number and composition of the population, development indicators.*

Key words: *population, demographic, collection, generalization, evaluation, categories, process, legal population, temporary departures, population list, level of knowledge, registration, analysis, promotion.*

When studying demographic processes directly using the question-and-answer, chat method, aspects that statistical data could not express are also covered. The study of demographic processes using socioeconomic research is called sociologodemographic research. With such a method of conducting research, it is possible to thoroughly study the characteristics, factors and problems of demographic processes, mainly by generations. Sociologo-demographic

studies are of great help in the study of the demographic situation, especially in areas where regular population censuses are not conducted. To do this, special questionnaires are drawn up by specialists in the study of demographic processes and distributed to the population or social groups of the area under study. also among the population, specialists conduct interviews based on the questionnaire and collect the necessary information. The socioeconomic style is even more

valuable, especially for regions where demographic processes in ancient times, such as Uzbekistan, were not regularly recorded in statistics. Because by conducting special sociological-demographic studies among the older generations, it is possible to gather information about what demographic processes were in ancient times and the factors that affected them, having a somewhat clear picture. The study of demographic processes in Uzbekistan with the help of sociological demographic research began in 1928-1930-ies. And since 1960-1970-ies became more and more perfect and developed.

The permanent registration of the population list and population allows you to get full information about the population by pushing each one. But there are also different sides to ulami. The population list is conducted by special organizations, specialists and simultaneously for certain periods (in most cases - in 10 years). And in the case of permanent account of the population, they come to the relevant organizations of the

population themselves within the period established by law and record the demographic process. In the regular determination of the number of population and the change in its composition, the data on the population list are basic. In a certain year, the population list is conducted and accurate information about the number and composition of the population is obtained. In order to determine the number and composition of the population in the next year, the number of people born and immigrants in this year is added to the number of the population determined in the list, and the number of those who died and moved is subtracted. With such a method, data on the number and composition of the population for each year are determined before the next population list is held.

With the help of this research, the processes such as birth, death, marriage and divorce in the urban and rural districts of the Republic and their relationship with the population have been studied separately in terms of generations, factors, characteristics have been identified. It is also

important to conduct sociological-Demographic Research in the study of the demographic process. Another important source, taking into account the population, is the information about individual groups of the population, which are collected by different organizations. For example, the list of voters (in Uzbekistan 0 people aged 18 and above have the right to elect, the information on the age, gender, social status of the Ulema is collected by the constituency of each city, village) lists of women of reproductive age (15-49) who are eligible for military service (men's main ages are registered in the military). It also collects information about the number of families and family members, farms in the neighborhood, rural civil councils.

The study of the demographic process in all countries of the world has its own history and features. The study of the demographic process in Uzbekistan is of great importance, as well as data on socio-economic development, recording the civil status accumulated through the activity of the statistic of the Republic of Uzbekistan

of the present day, consisting of the second half of the XIX century. The committee prepares and regularly publishes statistic Chronicles on the number of population of the Republic, natural growth, marriage and divorce, migration, health, socio-economic status. These chronicles serve as a scientific basis in determining the changes taking place in the demographic situation of Uzbekistan, defining the problem and developing the future. In the study of family and demographic process in Uzbekistan, population census data conducted in the territory of the country are also of great importance will earn.

According to scientific sources, the first population list in the Republic was held in 1897-th year, this population list could not cover the entire territory of the current Uzbekistan border. However, the data of this list will help to create a tasawur about demographic processes such as families, the number of population, ethnic composition, birth, death, who lived in Uzbekistan at the end of the XIX century. Later in Uzbekistan 1926, 1939, 1959, 1970,

1979, 1989-in the years, the population census was conducted. This is a population list!arida has valuable information in studying the demographic history of the country.

The demographic process is one of the important types of current account of the population carrying out continuous regular, continuous guuha1aa without interruption, and this process is mainly carried out by the authorities writing acts of civil status. These organizations constantly record and record cases of birth, death, marriage and divorce. Written evidence of civil status in the Republic of Uzbekistan (FHDSU) bodies are established within the framework of districts, regions, cities and full information about those who were born, died, recorded marriages, divorces, exact dates and persons of the Ulema is constantly recorded. In general, the savollami in the

demographic process registration program can be divided into two gumh. The first group includes the address of the processes, the time of occurrence and recording, and the second group includes the savollami about the persons who passed the process. For example, in the birth registration-the data such as the father of the baby, the nationality of his mother, the age, the place of work are also recorded. Even in the registration of the marriage process, information on the nationality, age and social status of the entrant in marriage is indicated. On the basis of this data, a lot of indicator tables are prepared. Such tables can illustrate the distribution of the birth by nationality, age, nationality of the father, age, by Regions, nationalities, age groups of the deceased, by marriage, by divorce, by such cases.

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